

[DigiReady+] Workshop1: Self-Assessment Instruments for Assessing Digital Readiness in HEIs - Storyboard

Date: [add date]

[NOTE: Please adjust roles and times according to your setup]

Color coding:

- **Yellow** = Start of small group activities
- **Green** = Start of common activities

[Note] if the main group < 5 people then all activities can be carried out in common

START common session			
Agenda Item/Topic	Platform & Method	Prompt/Invitation and Content	Timing of Sequence & Materials (add links when there)
Welcome /Icebreaker (Facilitator) 9:00 - 9:15 CET	Presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce ourselves - Introduce project & consortium - Introduce DR concepts - Present workshop topic and structure - Ask participants to sign the online consent form - Ask them if they agree with recording to type in the chat - ask participants to share a little bit about themselves and chat about any overlaps or interesting bits that you hear 	Materials: Slides , Consent Form , Agenda Total time: 15 min (max 20) Parallel todos: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Post link to slides in Zoom <input type="checkbox"/> Record session, upload recording and add link to schedule
Part 1 (Facilitator) 9:15 - 10:00 CET	Discussion	<p>A. Personal perspective: Discuss terms: Digital Readiness, Digital Transformation, Digital Maturity</p> <p><i>[Questions to guide discussion:]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Are participants familiar with terms? 	Materials: Slides, Notes taking Total time: 45 min Special notes:

•Have they met the terms within the work context?
How?

•Do they perceive DR as an important aspect?
Why?

B. DR within the Organization: Discuss Digital Readiness from the perspective of the Organization and participants' roles

[Questions to guide discussion:]

•Participants' **perception** about DR and the institution?

•Does the HEI **prioritize** DR? to what extent? How (examples)?

•Are there **policies or strategies** in place? Within the HEI? Top-down (from state/government)? Are there evaluation processes? Does the university use **self-assessment instruments**? yes/no/how

•How does the organization handle topics relating to **adoption and maintenance of technology**? Is there a specific department handling these topics? What are the specific responsibilities in terms of DR and what is the connection with government and other stakeholders?

•Who is responsible for the adoption and integration of technology in **teaching and learning** and digitalization of content? Is there a body or unit within the organization responsible for establishing and disseminating best practices? What are the incentives (if any) for promoting digital practices in teaching and learning?

•How are stakeholders **trained to use** technology for teaching and learning? What are the

- Involve each and every participant in the discussion
- Starting with the highest rank/authority role, follow up with others
- If one person dominates the discussion, try to put a full stop and involve others. For next discussion round, leave this person last

Note taking:

-one note-taker takes notes on a whiteboard (virtual) or on post-its and sticks them on a board.

- each time a note goes on the board, explicitly state that to your participants to make them aware of the existence of this note on the board.

- the facilitator should direct the note taker, what notes to put on the board.

- on the side, keep observation notes that will NOT be visible to participants

		<p>standards followed, who trains the stakeholders? Are there practices for establishing trust relationship between teachers and the organization? Is there a unit with the primary focus on providing technical support to stakeholders?</p> <p>•How are strategies or digital readiness plans communicated to the HEI community?</p> <p>•Challenges with existing planning</p>	
Break (20 minutes) 10:00 - 10:20 CET			
Part 2-section 1 (Facilitator) 10:20 - 10:50 CET	Hands-on activity (affinity diagram)	<p>•Introduce self-assessment instruments of Digital Readiness (5 minutes)</p> <p>•Present fundamental concepts /dimensions of assessment (5 minutes)</p> <p>•Ask participants to collaboratively categorize notes from Part 1 using concepts above (20 minutes). The notes should be categorized in the following categories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Leadership, 2. Policies and Strategies, 3. Teaching and Learning Practices, 4. Training and Support, 5. Content and Curricula, 6. Infrastructure <p>When done inform participants about breakout rooms and activity to follow up</p>	<p>Materials: Slides, Notes, Diagram (Board)</p> <p>Total time: 30 min</p> <p>Parallel todos:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Create breakout rooms</p>
Part 2-section 2 (Facilitator) 10:50 - 11:40 CET	Questionnaire, Discussion	•Activity: Fill in CoL questionnaire as a group (max. 15 minutes)	<p>Materials: Questionnaire, Slides (same as part2-section 1), Notes, Diagram</p> <p>Total time: 50 min</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •discuss questionnaire, focusing on differences and commonalities, usefulness, relevance, practicality for organization •Prepare presentation in breakout rooms for followup in the main room after break (15 minutes both) 	Parallel todos: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Message breakout rooms to inform about time two minutes before end
Break			
START common session			
Agenda Item/Topic	Platform & Method	Prompt/Invitation and Content	Timing of Sequence & Materials
Part 3 (Facilitator) 12:00 - 12:40	Reflections, Conversation Cafe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •One participant per breakout room presents their discussion and reflections on the questionnaire •Discussion on usefulness, relevance, practicality of self-assessment tools for the HEI 	Materials: Slides, participants' notes Total time: 40 min (alternatively: 30 minutes, 15 minutes moved to part 2) <input type="checkbox"/> Record session, upload recording and add link to schedule
Wrap-up (Facilitator) 12:40 - 13:00 CET	Outro presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Pitch for importance of data •Preparation for next workshop: Give homework! •Point out we will follow up with a report on the activity 3 weeks after the SECOND workshop. THANK PARTICIPANTS!	Materials: Slides Total Time: 15 min
END OF WORKSHOP			